

Annual Plan 2022 – 2023

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1 Message from the Director

Last year we celebrated the 5th anniversary of ODISSEI. In 5 short years we have come a long way. We have grown from just 23 member organisations in 2016 to 43 today. We have created the ODISSEI Secure Supercomputer for analysing highly sensitive data, provided rapid access to a world class, representative panel during the COVID-19 national lockdown, and provided access to high quality data to hundreds of researchers. We are proud of these and many other accomplishments.

In this annual plan, you will see how we plan to build on these achievements and instigate an evolution in ODISSEI, from a technical and groundbreaking infrastructure into a fully fledged and vibrant scientific community. With significant progress in the development of the ODISSEI Secure Supercomputer, the ODISSEI Portal and the increasing interoperability of data across the infrastructure, it is time to invite the social science community in and ensure that our investments can be leveraged to advance social research in the Netherlands and cement our position as global leaders in methodological and technical innovation.

To achieve this, we have several initiatives planned over the next year. This summer we will host the first ODISSEI Summer School for Computational Social Science which will provide early career researchers with an immersive series of workshops on using the ODISSEI infrastructure. The coordination team at Erasmus is also now helping researchers at ODISSEI member organisations to supercharge their research grants and make full use of the possibilities that ODISSEI offers. We will also be scaling up the work of our Social Data Science Team who have recently hired several great young talents with an eclectic set of expertise. They will be engaging with researchers across the ODISSEI member organisations and making sure that they can use all the services available to them. We will also deliver the first iterations of the ODISSEI Portal which will help researchers navigate the vast range of data that is available through ODISSEI. We hope all of these developments will be showcased through our annual conference in November which we have expanded and opened up so that this ODISSEI community continues to grow.

The next year will therefore be focused on delivering on the promise of ODISSEI and ensuring that all researchers can benefit from its services. After 5 years of intensive development, for me this is where the exciting work can truly begin

Pearl Dykstra
Scientific director, ODISSEI

2 Governance

ODISSEI now consists of **43 member organisations** who have all signed the participants agreement and committed their financial contribution to ODISSEI until 2024, the end of the Roadmap project.

The **Supervisory Board** consists of Pieter Hooimeijer (DSW, chair), Carlo Schuengel (DSW), Henk van der Kolk (DSW), Arthur van Soest (DEB), Hanneke Imbens (Statistics Netherlands), Helga de Valk (KNAW/NWO institutes and E-infrastructures), and Sander Steijn (public research institutes).

The **Management Board** consists of nine members: Pearl Dykstra (EUR, Chair and Director), Tom Emery (EUR, Deputy Director), Dorret Boomsma (VU), Tanja van der Lippe (UU), Marcel Das (Centerdata), Ruben Dood (Statistics Netherlands), Annette Langedijk (SURF), Rob van Nieuwpoort (NLeSC), Henk Wals (DANS), and Jacco van Ossenbruggen (VU). The Management Board meets monthly to discuss and evaluate the program of work.

The Coordination Team now consists of eight individuals Pearl Dykstra (Director), Tom Emery (Deputy Director), Lucas van der Meer (Operational Manager), Kasia Karpinska (Scientific Manager), Suze Zijlstra (Community Manager), Godelieve de Wijer (Community Manager), Angelica Maineri (Data Manager), and Sofia den Haan (Project Management Officer).

An **International Advisory Board** has been established including Ron Dekker (Project Director Open Science at Technopolis Group Belgium, Consortium), Julia Lane (New York University), Melinda Mills (University of Oxford), Sally Wyatt (Maastricht University), and Amy O'Hara (Georgetown University). Due to travel restrictions the board has yet to meet in person, but a virtual meeting took place in May 2021.

3 Programme of Work

ODISSEI conducts activities in four work streams as defined in the ODISSEI Roadmap proposal: the Data Facility, the Observatory, the Laboratory, and the Hub. This section details those activities and the work that is planned for the period 2022-2023.

3.1 The Data Facility

3.1.1 CBS Microdata Access

ODISSEI stimulates the use of the rich microdata at Statistics Netherlands (CBS), particularly amongst early career researchers and first-time users. In early 2022, ODISSEI launched its annual call to facilitate access to microdata from Statistics Netherlands free of charge for researchers at ODISSEI member organisations (so-called Microdata Access Grants, MAG). Around six projects will be granted in Summer 2022 with a total allocation of **€ 60,000**. The amounts awarded are small with an average amount of € 7,500 but the impact of access is large, and these projects would not be possible without them. ODISSEI will continue the Microdata Access Discount (MAD) in collaboration with Statistics Netherlands. ODISSEI provides a discount of up to 50% to Statistics Netherlands microdata projects from ODISSEI member organisations. The total value of these discounts for the coming year is **€ 240,000**. A full list of projects that receive the discount is available on the ODISSEI website.

Resocialisation and recidivism during the corona-crisis

In the midst of the corona crisis, prisoners are faced with several measures that are meant to avoid a corona-outbreak in prison, such as the suspension of visits and re-integration activities. After release from prison, ex-prisoners have to deal with 'the new normal' in our society; they are faced with social distancing, the task to stay at home as much as possible, and institutions that can only be reached by phone or e-mail. This may mean that the corona-crisis has had a negative impact on prisoners' ability to reintegrate back into society and to refrain from further offending. Using a MAG grant, Elanie Rodermond (NCSR/VU) is examining post-release outcomes and recidivism of individuals who have been released from prison during the corona-crisis. The project uses data from the Custodial Institutions Agency, complemented with data from Statistics Netherlands. A subsample of prisoners are followed during their transition into society. Findings will shed light on how former prisoners fared during the corona-crisis and inform policymakers and practitioners tasked with providing pre- and post-release programs for and support to (ex)prisoners.

In addition to access grants and discounts, CBS will spend **€134,000** on further innovations to improve the efficiency and performance of microdata services. These include the enhancement of metadata that will be ingested by the ODISSEI Portal, the automation of procedures for initiating a new project, the transition from Citrix to VMWARE for use in the CBS Remote Access Environment, and continued research into the implementation of automated disclosure checks. These investments in efficiency are vital as demand for microdata continues to increase rapidly and the need for scalability is intensified.

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3.1.2 ODISSEI Secure Supercomputer

Statistics Netherlands and SURF transitioned the ODISSEI Secure Supercomputer (OSSC) to the new national Supercomputer Snellius, in May 2022. This facility is a global first enabling the analysis of highly sensitive administrative data that is linked to data from social surveys and other sources in a secure HPC environment. The ODISSEI Secure Supercomputer provides the fastest computing capacity in the Netherlands via the national supercomputer and obeys the highest standards for data protection both legally and technically. In May 2022, the OSSC demonstrated its security by passing a penetration test performed by the digital security company Secura¹.

The Effects of Spatial Planning Policy

There is a heated policy discussion about the need to construct new dwellings. A vital point of this discussion is where to locate this new residential construction. Some suggest looking to the past, to the last large-scale spatial planning programme in the Netherlands, the VINEX. In cooperation with Utrecht University, the Netherlands Environmental Assessment Agency (PBL) is researching the long-term effects of the VINEX policy on the housing- and labour market.

The goal of this project is to analyse the long-term effects of the VINEX using a quasi-experimental research design, to investigate whether moving to a VINEX location had a discernible impact on an individual's labour- or housing-market position. Leveraging the rich microdata from CBS, the researchers construct a longitudinal dataset, consisting of a large number of variables, covering

Operation of the OSSC will cost **€ 159,216** in 2022-2023 which is exclusively for SURF. A further **€ 479,267** is planned for the development of the OSSC environment for research, which is shared between SURF and CBS. This includes the costs of a penetration test and adaptations to ensure the OSSC can service all member organisations. The OSSC was formally launched in October 2020 and now has capacity to support 15 projects per year. There have been delays in initiating projects due to the transfer of the OSSC from Cartesius to Snellius but these delays are now resolved. Interest in the OSSC has been considerable and comes from a wide variety of member organisations, as well as from organisations that are not

¹ www.secura.com/penetration-testing

ODISSEI members. Through 2022-23 it is hoped that a further 7 projects will be supported in their implementation and usage of OSSC with the Coordination Team monitoring progress.

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3.2 The Observatory

3.2.1 ODISSEI Data Collection Committee

The ODISSEI Data Collection Committee facilitates collaboration and aims to transition the long-standing data collections into a coherent and sustainable future in which they are well placed within a more diverse and dynamic data landscape. ODISSEI ensures Dutch participation in cross-national data collections works to identify critical gaps in the data landscape and allocate resources to sustain longitudinal data collections. The Data Collection Committee will support data collections transition to sustainable operational models, the integration of new data collection methodologies and linkages with secure, register data via the Data Facility. Four members have been appointed: Marike Knoef (Chair), Gerbert Kraaykamp, Ineke Stoop, and Bella Struminskaya. Tom Emery acts as the Coordination Team support for the committee.

In 2022-23 the committee will be overseeing the implementation and reporting of the European Social Survey, the Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe, and the Generations and Gender Survey. Once collected these data will be integrated into the international archives by their respective central hubs and made available for registered users. ODISSEI finances Dutch participation in ERIC surveys and surveys of key strategic importance. In 2022-23, ODISSEI is financing data collection for the European Social Survey (€ 445,000). ODISSEI will also pay the Dutch contribution for the Luxembourg Income Study (€ 30,000).

As Chair of the Data Collection Committee, Marike Knoef also oversees a data scout, Marco Stam, who identifies new sources of data for integration within ODISSEI (the ODISSEI Data Portal, linkage to CBS Microdata, use of secure data environments etc), especially data that has not been collected for research purposes and particularly in the fields of Law and Economics which are currently under-represented within the ODISSEI framework. Marco works with potential data providers and existing ODISSEI services to facilitate access to such data sets, ensure their adequate documentation and promote their usage.

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3.2.2 Historical Sample of the Netherlands

To support links between historical and contemporary data on social processes, data from the Historical Sample of the Netherlands (HSN) is being linked with Statistics Netherlands Microdata (Social Statistical Database SSD). In practical terms, this involves the creation of a key for the persistent identifiers of individuals in the HSN and the persistent identifier for the same individual in the Social Statistical Database which is available in ODISSEI via CBS microdata services. Using this link, it is possible to trace the outcomes of the individuals in the HSN and their descendants forward to the current day. This enables connections between the historical research conducted using the HSN and contemporary society and the outcomes studied by social scientists. This line of research has also enabled stronger links with CLARIAH and the broader field of socio-economic history more generally.

Figure 1 - Lexis diagram showing the main sources of the HSN's life course data and the integration with the SSD dataset and the censuses of 1960 and 1971

The budget allocated for HSN in 2022-2023 is € 111,493. In 2021-22, 84% of the 1900-1922 HSN Cohort was linked with CBS microdata. In 2022-23 a Data coordinator will curate the linked data and coordinate with a team at Statistics Netherlands on its documentation. A research assistant will help with data cleaning and linkage of the HSN cohorts and the linkage with SSD data, and staff at Statistics Netherlands will ensure that the data is prepared for use in research through the CBS remote access environment.

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3.2.3 National Twin Registry

The work conducted by the National Twin Register (NTR) focuses on linking biomedical and cognitive data with the wider ODISSEI infrastructure through proof-of-concept projects within the ODISSEI Secure Supercomputer and integrating and consolidating existing research on pedigrees across microdata projects at Statistics Netherlands. The work forms a key bridge to the work conducted in Consortium on Individual Development (CID)² and BBMRI (Netherlands Biobank Research Facility)³ and consists of two tasks.⁴

The first task is to broaden the scope of record linkage of cohort data and CBS data conducted as part of the OSSC pilot to include multiple external cohorts. The goal is to build on the procedures set up by the NTR teams and develop a standard operating procedure (SOP) within the new national SuperComputer, Snellius, for linking and analysing multiple external data sources with CBS data at once. This will allow for the pooling of cohorts and subsequent linkage to CBS microdata, greatly increasing the diversity of research questions that can be answered about specific sub-populations.

The second task defines a thorough network of family ties in the CBS data by including the classifications of genetic resemblance and creating a standardized method of defining family ties. Currently, the genetic and social pedigree structures are limited because information on parent-offspring relationships, that forms the basis for pedigree definitions, is often only available for two generations: children born after 1966, and their parents, and does not differentiate between biological and non-biological parents (see task 3.2.3). These data will be enriched with information from various sources to generate a comprehensive network of family ties that includes the genetic resemblance of all individuals in the Netherlands. Possibilities for differentiating between mono- and dizygotic twins based on CBS microdata or other external data sources (e.g. perined.nl, palgaopenbaredatabank.nl) will be developed. The budget for this work in 2021-22 will be **€ 87,398**.

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² individualdevelopment.nl

³ bbmri.nl

⁴ unsplash.com/@nci

3.3 The Laboratory

3.3.1 Distributed Analytics

Data about people are sensitive owing to privacy concerns and issues relating to data protection. This task explores the use of novel privacy-preserving technologies in order to understand the influence of special needs students in relation to the health and well-being of their teachers and other students. Achieving this objective requires legitimate access to data that are collected and maintained by different organisations, with different policies concerning

their potential reuse. The overall objective of this work is to explore the feasibility of applying privacy-preserving technologies to achieve this objective. The work is made up of 3 sub-tasks:

Privacy-preserving technology: Develop methods that expose metadata in such a way that it does not reveal specific and privacy-sensitive attributes of a particular population, but rather exposes a constrained vocabulary that could be used to query the target data.⁵

Legal-ethical framework: Identify possible legal routes for the proposed research to occur, with a particular emphasis on the role that privacy-preserving technologies can play in fostering trust, transparency, and accountability.

Social science research: A scalable and reproducible statistical pipeline on social-emotional metrics from questionnaires. The pipeline will consider alternative proxies for current metrics. Before being prototyped on real queries, the pipeline will be developed using synthetic data testing the scalability and reproducibility parts.

The project team collaborates with Netherlands Initiative for Education Research (NRO), who maintains close connections to the schools who will make available the education-related data, and with a researcher of the Inspectorate of Education, who seeks to perform the analysis, and finally with Statistics Netherlands (CBS), who has relevant microdata and has established a research-grade secure computing environment to undertake privacy-preserving research. For the year 2022-23, the budget of this task is € 98,583 which is exclusively for project staff.

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⁵ Photo credit: <https://unsplash.com/@taypaigey>

3.3.2 Automated Linkage

This task is focused on applying innovations in information science to enhance the work conducted within the portal. The ODISSEI Portal aims to make research datasets findable by providing an advanced search interface on the data records describing these data sets. We refer to these records as the metadata. The better the quality of these metadata records, the better the Portal's functionality. While the main responsibility for providing high-quality metadata lies with the data owners and data providers in the project, it is expected that (semi) automatic enrichment of metadata of ODISSEI datasets can also help to improve the metadata used in the Portal.

The goal of this task is to design and develop methods and techniques for (semi) automatic enrichment of metadata of ODISSEI datasets. Special focus is on improving metadata for sensitive datasets, to help researchers 1) find these datasets and 2) help them assess their applicability to their research before requesting access to the actual data.

An example of this is the codification of data access conditions and licensing. Information about data constraints has been extracted from the licence and policy agreements applied to the data. This includes information such as whether the data can be used for academic or commercial purposes, if the data can be downloaded, if the data allows for derivative works, how attribution must be given to original work. Such information is not intrinsically present in the metadata, and therefore this process significantly enhances the interoperability and reusability of data. Crucially, this codification makes the licensing and data access requirements machine actionable and has the potential to greatly improve the efficiency of data access across ODISSEI in the future.

For the year 2021-22, the budget of this task is € 73,918 which is exclusively for project staff.

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3.3.3 The LISS panel

The LISS panel, managed by Centerdata, consists of some 7,000 individuals from approximately 4,500 households. The panel is a representative sample of the adult population in the Netherlands. In May 2022, ODISSEI launched the fifth round of the **LISS Grant**. The calls are exceptionally popular. Successful projects are showcased on the ODISSEI website⁶ and generate considerable press attention. The call closes on 23 September.

All proposals that meet the eligibility criteria are assessed by the Centerdata team for feasibility. They are then submitted for peer-review. Reviewers' scores will be returned by the end of November and the decision announced by mid-December. The projects will commence from February 2022. These calls cost **€ 95,000** for 2021-22.

In addition to the LISS Grants, ODISSEI will provide a **€ 175,000 subsidy to the LISS panel**. This budget will be used for the maintenance of the LISS panel in 2022-2023. These fixed annual costs include personnel costs for panel management, subscription of broadband connection for panel members with initially no internet access, maintenance of hardware on loan to panel members, server and software licence costs, and incentive costs for updating background variables and activation of 'sleeping' panel members (as to avoid attrition). Costs for the core study mainly consist of incentives for panel members, but also personnel costs for programming, testing, data cleaning and data dissemination.

As a recognition to ODISSEI of the provided subsidy, Centerdata provides a 20% discount for using the LISS panel to projects from ODISSEI member organisations. In 2021-22, the ODISSEI coordination team evaluated the performance of the LISS call and its ability to stimulate innovative research and widen access. Minor amendments to the LISS call for 2022 were subsequently implemented to allow a more diverse range of proposals to be submitted, including from larger groups of researchers. The success of these changes will be evaluated in 2022-23.

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⁶ odissei-data.nl/en/2020/04/odissei-funds-corona-research-in-the-liss-panel

3.4 The Hub

3.4.1 Community Management

ODISSEI has more than forty member organisations and is open for others to join. There are a lot of potential users whose research would benefit from the infrastructure ODISSEI offers. Some have heard of the possibilities, but do not know ODISSEI can support them in using the infrastructure. Others already use ODISSEI but are not aware of all the infrastructure has to offer. It is important that they continue to stay involved or use the infrastructure more widely. The goal of Community Management is, first, to ensure that all potential users in relevant

disciplines have high-quality knowledge of ODISSEI so they can understand its use and importance (**inform**). Researchers should be encouraged to take the next step in engagement with ODISSEI (**involve**). Those who are already involved should be stimulated to stay involved to broaden and deepen their involvement (**engage**). For that purpose, Community Management will deploy a wide range of activities:

Inform:

- Newsletter
- Website
- Posts on Twitter and LinkedIn.
- Knowledge clips
- Podcast series

Involve:

- Annual conference
- Task Insights meetings
- Active Slack Community
- Lunch lecture series

Engage:

- Grant information workshops
- Roadshows & ODISSEI Q&A sessions
- Partner events

The community management costs for 2021-22 are **€ 324,053** and include the costs of the ODISSEI coordination team, all events and wider project management.

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3.4.2 Educational Programme

In 2022 ODISSEI is organising the first [ODISSEI Summer School in Computational Social Science](#) in collaboration with [SICSS](#). This summer school will provide 20 participants with two full weeks of intensive training in network analysis, machine learning and benchmark approaches (see section 3.4.5). The program of the summer school will be delivered by SoDa, the Benchmark team, the eScience Center, and Coordination Team. The curriculum makes extensive use of both LISS panel data and CBS administrative data. This summer school is designed to fill a gap in graduate school curriculums that are unable to provide the access and training necessary to use complex elements of the ODISSEI infrastructure. In 2023, a repeat and potential expansion of the summer school is planned and ODISSEI intends to have the summer school accredited with ECTS points for graduate students. The summer school is therefore a crucial means of creating a new generation of computational social scientists who can fully utilize the infrastructure.

The summer school compliments a broader programme of workshops that is geared towards using specific ODISSEI facilities, with workshops tailored to potential and current users of ODISSEI facilities, such as the Microdata Access Grant and Discount, the LISS panel Grant and the ODISSEI Secure Supercomputer. These workshops aim to inform researchers of the ins and outs of ODISSEI facilities and lower the threshold for submitting a project proposal. The programme is developed in collaboration with, and executed by or together with, several ODISSEI partners: Data Archiving and Networked Services (DANS), CBS, Centerdata, Netherlands eScience Center (NLeSC) and SURF.

The team also works with the graduate schools and ODISSEI member organizations to coordinate existing efforts and where feasible identify and help address gaps in the existing provision of training and education in the Dutch Computational Social Science community. For 2022-23, the educational team will deliver approximately 5 workshops aimed at using the ODISSEI infrastructure and focused on thematic areas of interest such as geospatial analysis or network analysis. The costs of operating the ODISSEI educational programme for 2021-22 are **€ 91,013** and include the costs of coordination and resources for hosting events, including the ODISSEI Summer School.

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3.4.3 ODISSEI Social Data Science

The Social Data Science (SoDa) team bridges the gap between applied social scientists and the data, computing, and analytical infrastructure provided by ODISSEI. They seek out short-term collaborative projects with social scientists across ODISSEI member organisations, uniquely leverage ODISSEI's infrastructure to answer novel substantive questions, and build expertise in computational social science. These projects result not only in 'traditional' publications, but also in open-source reusable code that can be used for teaching purposes or as a starting point for other projects. The team supports researchers using other components of the infrastructure such as the OSSC, Microdata, eScience or LISS. In 2021-22, SoDa took on 10 projects and has capacity to take on further projects and collaborations through 2022-23.

Examples of SoDa Projects 2021-22

Deviance in Art. SoDa is assisting Eftychia Stamkou (UvA) in creating a model to distinguish deviant art from conventional art using machine learning with text and images. SoDa has also written code for data collection (a Wikiart and Google Art&Culture scraper) which has resulted in a Python package.

Spread of COVID-19 through Networks. Together with RIVM and the ministry of health, the SoDa team is exploring how to analyze the spread of COVID-19 in social networks, making use of the CBS population network files. The outcome of the project is a report for the ministry of health, and a scientific paper currently in development.

Empathy diagnostics dashboard. Together with psychologist Minet de Wied (UU), the SoDa team is exploring ways to make the results of a diagnostic survey immediately available through an [RShiny app](#) visualization, so that they can be discussed as a diagnostic tool.

Anonymity-preserving analysis of whatsapp data. The SoDa team is helping Laura Boeschoten & Rense Corten (UU) to create a script to extract information from Whatsapp data packages, allowing users to link data from different people while preserving their privacy. This project is part of the ODISSEI LISS grant "Assessing Mobile Instant Messenger Networks with Donated Data".

Synthetic data. Funding has been acquired by the SoDa team from Utrecht University and the CBS for a PhD project surrounding privacy-preserving generation of synthetic data. SoDa collaborates with other researchers working on synthetic data generation across ODISSEI.

The SoDa team is growing rapidly and consists of Daniel Oberski (PI), Erik-Jan van Kesteren (Team Leader), Jonathan de Bruin, Javier Garcia Bernardo, Parisa Zahedi, Shiva Nadi, and Raoul Schram. This

team has the capacity to increase the number of projects conducted during 2022-2023 and costs € 167,582.

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3.4.4 eScience Grants

In this task grants are provided for computational social science to support the use of the data infrastructure developed across ODISSEI. These grants provide hours from eScience Research Engineers (RSEs) employed at the eScience center to collaborate with social scientists and enhance their research by exploiting digital technologies. The grants are available via an [annual open call](#), which is assessed by a panel with members from ODISSEI and the eScience center. The deadline for the period 2021-2022 is September 6th 2022. An online information event for this call was held on 14th June. The call in 2022 is exclusively for small pathfinder grants (405 engineering hours with a value of € 25K). These pathfinders are pilot projects suitable for researchers just starting in the field, to explore the use of digital technologies for their research. Five projects will be granted in 2022-23 and in conjunction with coordination costs and alignment with SoDa, the budget is € 191,833. In subsequent years, larger grants will be available for more ambitious projects.

This produces a staircase approach to computational support, where researchers can ask for more support in larger projects, if needed. This staircase can start with consultancy from the SoDa team, followed by an eScience pathfinder grant, and ultimately a larger eScience grant. Finally, this process also ensures that the researchers are well positioned to apply for a full project in the eScience center open calls. Vice versa, successful eScience projects may lead to new SoDa followup projects as well. In addition to the open call for proposals, eScience Center can be engaged in ad-hoc projects throughout ODISSEI such as the ODISSEI Summer School and consulting on OSSC projects.

Example: Modelling consequences for school segregation with an agent-based model

School segregation by ethnicity and socio-economic status is a persistent problem in many educational systems. Existing research has mostly looked at at macro-level trends or parents independent school choice. But school choice is a complex system where parents' decisions are based on and reactive to the choices of other parents. Better modelling of this complex system could lead to a much better understanding of the dynamics that reinforce social segregation in schools. In this project from the 2021 call, a research team led by Andreas Flache will work with Engineers at eScience to explicitly model these dynamics in an Agent-Based Model (ABM) using the ODISSEI Secure Supercomputer and incorporating empirical data from CBS on multiple levels (e.g., households, schools, institutions) to study the consequences of interdependent, yet uncoordinated individual choices for the emergence of school segregation.

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3.4.5 Benchmarking

Benchmarking is about creating a system of reference, in which various models that address the same task can be compared, in order to be able to analyse the strength and weaknesses of various approaches and gain new insights. For computer scientists, benchmarks provide a standardized way to validate predictive models that have proven to be able to detect major breakthroughs, like deep learning. For example, when Geoffrey Hinton submitted his convolutional neural network AlexNet to the ImageNet challenge (a computer vision benchmark) it showed a dramatic increase in performance, which boosted the field of neural networks and artificial intelligence in general.

The aim of this task is to design and set-up a benchmark for social sciences that addresses a real-world problem that social scientists are working on and preferably draws from various data sources. This task will deploy benchmarking challenges using ODISSEI infrastructure which would be the first social science benchmark to utilise linked administrative data. To achieve this, a benchmarking challenge is embedded within the ODISSEI Summer School. In the second week of the summer school, participants will be separated into small teams and given access to CBS microdata and challenged to predict several individual level outcomes. In the 2022 iteration of the summer school, the participants will be asked to predict levels of institutional trust amongst the population using linked surveys and administrative data. The topic of the challenge was set out by the Social and Cultural Planbureau.

In 2021-2022 the cost of coordinating the benchmarking project will be € 21,719 for the year, and run until the end of the roadmap project with a challenge embedded in each subsequent ODISSEI Summer School. The work will be led by Paulina Pankowska in collaboration with the coordination team and SoDa.

Task Leader: Paulina K. Pankowska

Coordination Team Contact: Tom Emery (tom@odissei-data.nl)

Management Board Contact: Rob van Nieuwpoort (R.vanNieuwpoort@esciencecenter.nl)

4 Financial Plan 2022-2023

ODISSEI aligned the reporting schedule of (a) the Task Leaders to the Management Board, (b) the Management Board to the Supervisory Board, and (c) ODISSEI to NWO. For this reason, the financial year runs from 1 July to 30 June. The table below summarises the financial allocations requested by the task leaders and approved by the Management Board for the year 2022-2023. This is in line with the budget proposals in the initial roadmap application. For a specific description of each task and the use of its budget, please see section 3.

Table 2 – Budget Plan for 2022-2023 (with 2020-21 & 2021-22 for reference)

	(in €)	2020-2021	2021-2022	2022-2023
Data Facility		1,190,961	906,994	1,394,437
1.1 CBS Microdata		394,000	360,000	444,000
1.2 Use Cases		40,000	45,412	45,861
1.3 ODISSEI Secure Supercomputer		615,223	245,998	638,483
1.4 Portal		141,738	255,585	266,093
Observatory		294,630	1,267,844	808,355
2.1 Data collection		252,439	1,045,909	609,464
2.2 Media Content Analysis Lab		-	69,005	-
2.1 Historical Sample of NL		42,191	82,021	111,493
2.1 Netherlands Twin Register		-	70,909	87,398
Laboratory		427,219	720,867	442,501
3.1 Distributed Learning		66,216	81,746	98,583
3.2 Automatic Linking		70,909	72,398	73,918
3.4 LISS panel		260,000	520,000	270,000
3.4 Mass Online Experiments		30,094	46,724	-
3.5 Citizen Science		-	-	-
Hub		580,233	1,037,697	887,877
4.1 Community management		230,437	508,061	415,728
4.2 Education		10,000	90,376	91,013
4.3 Social Data Science team		173,463	224,257	167,582
4.4 eScience Grants		166,333	191,833	191,833
4.5 Benchmarking		-	23,170	21,719
Total		2,493,043	3,933,402	3,533,170

5 Key Performance Indicators

ODISSEI maintains a register of Key Performance Indicators (KPI) that were initiated at the beginning of the current Roadmap period. Each year the current status of each KPI is reported upon and new targets are established. The KPI are proposed by the Coordination Team and Management Board and amended and approved by the ODISSEI Supervisory Board to ensure continuity and alignment with regards to the specific and concrete aims of the project.

Table 3 - Key Performance Indicators

Indicator	Target	Current
Development		
Participation of all social science and economics faculties	All social science and economics faculties to be full ODISSEI members by 2025	All social science faculties are members. 6 of 15 Economics faculties still have to sign up to join.
Participation in European projects	Active participation in at least two European Level projects by 2025	ODISSEI is now a partner in SoBigData Europe and investigating further projects.
International infrastructure collaborations	Formal collaboration with similar initiatives in UK, US, FR, and DE by 2024	Initial contact has been made with discussion of formalisation
Data Access & Analysis		
Percentage of researchers at ODISSEI member organisations submitting a proposal	Receive project proposals from 10% of researchers at ODISSEI member organisations	Currently approximately 7% of all researchers have submitted
Percentage of researchers at ODISSEI member organisations being granted a project	Provide access to 5% of researchers at ODISSEI member organisations by 2025	Currently 1% of all researchers have received a grant
Number of unique visitors to the ODISSEI Portal	No current target set (To be set in 2023)	None as Portal is still in development
Number of OSSC Projects per year	7 per year for 2022, 2023 and 2024	6 in 2021
Number of projects spanning more than 2 service providers	5 per year by 2025	4 projects in 2021
Financial		
Further successful funding applications	Participation in a successful 2022 Roadmap Application for SSH	2022 Roadmap proposal and SSO proposal submitted
Total amount committed by member organisations	By 2025, to receive continuation of existing commitments to 2029 as a minimum	Current contributions are perpetual but no commitments until 2029
Training & Education		
Number of attendees at training events and workshops	600 unique attendees at events per year	404 for 2020-2021

Number of projects supported by Social Data Analytics Team (SoDa) *15 projects completed before end of 2024* *10 projects acquired up to April 2022*

Science & Technology

Number of scientific papers describing the infrastructure *3 per year by 2025* *2 in 2021*

Number of peer-reviewed publications derived from ODISSEI supported research projects *30 per year by 2025* *8 in 2020-2021*

Number of citations received for publications derived from ODISSEI supported research projects *200 per year by 2025* *23 in 2020-2021*

Social and Economic Impact

Number of datasets contributed by non-academic organisations *Five datasets from non-academic organisations accessible by 2025* *2*

Number of government agencies participating as member organisations *7 by 2025* *6*

Number of website visits *50,000 per year by 2025* *9,200 in 2020-2021*

Mentions in key policy documents *3 per year* *Monitoring as of 2022*

Press mentions of ODISSEI related research in the Netherlands *10 per year* *Monitoring as of 2022*

Communication

Number of social media (e.g. Twitter, LinkedIn) subscribers *5,000 by 2025* *986*

Number of newsletter subscribers *Total of 1,000 by 2025* *596*

Attracting New Talent

Number of international scientists recruited by ODISSEI *20 by the end of 2024* *TBC*

Number of major grants using ODISSEI (e.g. NWO talent, MCSA, ERC etc) *5 per year* *2 in 2021*

6 Risk Register

The ODISSEI Risk register is designed to support the strategic planning and decision making of the Coordination Team, the Management Board and the Supervisory Board. The risks identified by each task leader are consolidated into a single risk register. The full risk register appears at the end of this document and has been used to create an overview of the various challenges faced by ODISSEI. Risk assessments are always subjective but consolidating the risk assessments into a singular document can help identify common risks, differences in risk perceptions across the project and interdependent mitigation strategies. We start by reflecting on the perceived high probability, high impact risks from 2021 (see table 4).

Previous Risks

Table 4 - Former Perceived High Probability, High Impact Risks in 2021

Task	Mitigation
1.1 Unequal usage of the MAD across scientific domains and categories of users	Reconsider the discount distribution model
1.3 A new Supercomputer will arrive at SURF before 2024. The team must adopt to the new Supercomputer environment.	Once it is known what the new supercomputer is (in terms of hardware, software, operating system), the team will plan for transition of OSSC to the new Supercomputer. A transition period will be determined to have the OSSC running on the current supercomputer, while setting up and configuring the service on the new Supercomputer.
2.1 No further funding for data collections	The financing strategy must identify cost reduction measures and a new financing strategy and stimulate the respective survey communities to collaborate on funding applications
4.1 Limited opportunity for in-person meetings, due to the corona crisis	The team will select the best possible software for online events. The team will adapt the programme to make it suitable for an online event.
4.5 No interest from social scientists	Involving social scientists from before start of design through sessions at conferences

All the risks from 2021 have been resolved or mitigated in the last year. The MAD discount has been adjusted to redistribute usage more evenly across institutions by imposing a cap of 100% of membership fees on usage which has reduced the risk of unequal access across member organisations. As of May 2022, the new Supercomputer at SURF is hosting the OSSC. The risk of no financing for fieldwork past 2024 has also been reduced through the submission of several funding proposals aimed at ensuring continuity in data collections. There is also a considerably reduced impact of the pandemic on ODISSEI's ability to host in-person events. In 2021, there was also perceived high risk of the benchmarking not

being able to attract social scientists interest, but this has been almost entirely mitigated by embedding the benchmarking within the ODISSEI summer school.

Current Risks

The current high probability, high impact risks identified by Task Leaders, the Coordination Team and the Management Board are listed in table 5. All the risks have been explicitly discussed by the Management Board and are being actively monitored by task leaders and Coordination Team contacts.

A core risk is the misalignment between SURF and CBS in relation to the development of the OSSC and usage by researchers. This is due to staff turnover initially in SURF and more recently at CBS. It is being addressed through a reconfiguration of the OSSC working group and a shift in focus to operational projects after the transition to Snellius.

The second risk refers to issues of staff recruitment and retention in the Portal task where there has also been significant turnover. However, this is a trend that is not unique to Portal task members and has been observed across ODISSEI. ODISSEI tasks require complex translational skills and advanced technical, practical and scientific knowledge. Ensuring high quality recruitment, as well as training and development opportunities is a considerable challenge in ODISSEI. There has been high staff turnover at DANS, SURF, and CBS during the course of the project and many of those implementing tasks are developing highly specific technical knowledge that is of great value. Retention and development of these individuals is of high importance. The Coordination Team is responsible for this risk and will be consulting with a range of partners to assess how talent can be attracted and retained within ODISSEI.

The final risk is one that has increased in likelihood in the past year. MCAL has not been well embedded within the wider ODISSEI community and it remains a challenge to systematically and actively engage with similar associated projects across the community. Greater emphasis on task insight meetings and collaborative events are being set out by the community managers. It is also important that technical integration is accelerated and this should be supported by the new PDI-SSH project on FAIR implementation profiles which will establish a coherent FAIR community for social science across the Netherlands.

Table 5 - High Probability, High Impact Risks

<i>Task</i>	<i>Mitigation</i>
1.3 Misalignment between SURF and CBS	The team will have periodic meetings
1.4 Not being able to hire and retain appropriate staff	Widely setting out vacancies, possibility to outsource the hiring.
2.2 MCAL not embedded in wider ODISSEI community	Ensure regular contact between MCAL team and wider ODISSEI Tasks

Table 6 - Full Risk Register

Task	num	Risk	Prob	Imp	Mitigating Action	Risk Area
Data Facility						
1.1	1	Restrictions in the usage of CBS microdata, e.g., as a follow-up of the external investigation into the security of Microdata Services	1	3	Increase technical and procedural safety warrants so that the research process itself is not affected more than necessary	Legal
1.1	2	Lack of documentation in English limits the usability for non-Dutch researcher	3	2	CBS Data Service Centre next generation is aiming for including metadata description in English, but realization is still uncertain	FAIR
1.1	3	Increased usage to an extent that the MAD percentage to an undesirably low level, that might cause some members to consider leaving ODISSEI	2	2	Reconsider the discount distribution model	High Demand
1.1	4	Unequal usage of the MAD across scientific domains and categories of users	2	3	Reconsider the discount distribution model	Low Demand
1.1	5	Innovations selected as most useful according to the user need inventory are not feasible within time and budget	1	2	Propose smaller scale, stepwise innovations in agreement with the user council	Sustainability
1.1	6	Innovations proposed in the user need inventory are not compatible with the new safety regulations that results from the CBS re-evaluation of the safety of the RA facility	2	2	Adapt the proposals to fit the safety regulations or select different measures from the inventory	Legal
1.3	1	Failure of Cartesius hardware/software could mean down time for OSSC	2	3	Build and migrate as soon as possible to Snellius.	Technical
1.3	2	Misalignment between SURF and CBS	3	3	The team will have periodic meetings	Coordination
1.3	3	Too difficult user interface	2	2	Working on a graphic interface, education (Roadmap task 4.2)	Technical
1.3	4	Pentest results could cause delay on migration	2	2	Use Cartesius as long as possible	Technical
1.3	5	OSSC compatibility with Snellius reduced or lost due to changes	1	3	Include OSSC regression test during upgrades/changes	Technical
1.4	1	Not being able to hire and retain appropriate staff	3	3	Widely setting out vacancies, possibility to outsource the hiring.	Staffing
1.4	2	Misalignment (strategic or technical) between the partners	2	3	Bi-weekly, low-profile steering group and technical meetings	Coordination
1.4	3	Potential metadata providers not willing to or able to (automatically) share metadata, or to invest in altering metadata	2	3	Representatives in the ODISSEI Management Board. Cooperating with the ODISSEI Fieldwork Committee. Offering support to metadata providers.	FAIR
1.4	4	Insufficient need for what we develop	2	3	Three-monthly user tests, presenting early versions at conferences, creating use cases, close collaboration with the social science research community.	Low Demand

Task	num	Risk	Prob	Imp	Mitigating Action	Risk Area
1.4	5	Challenge to integrate the different components into one system	2	2	Coordination between partners and commonly designing technical infrastructure	Coordination
1.4	6	Lack of commitment for sustaining infrastructure after period 4	1	3	DANS committed to sustain the built infrastructure for at least five years.	Sustainability
1.4	7	Insufficient knowledge and consensus on explicit semantics of social-science metadata to develop a search interface with sufficient added value for social science researchers	2	3	Make use of existing standardisation efforts in the community, including the CESSDA metadata models and thesauri.	FAIR
Observatory						
2.1	1	High non-response in online data collections	3	2	Knowledge exchange and shared results of online data collection	Technical
2.1	2	Disruptions to fieldwork due to COVID	2	2	Most data collection has now been transferred to online only	Technical
2.1	3	Low cooperation with data scouts	2	1	Data Scouts need to be well embedded within the ODISSEI community and aware of the value added by ODISSEI	Coordination
2.1	4	No further funding for data collections	2	3	The financing strategy must identify cost reduction measures and a new financing strategy and stimulate the respective survey communities to collaborate on funding applications	Sustainability
2.2	1	Not embedded in wider ODISSEI community	3	3	Ensure regular contact between MCAL team and wider ODISSEI Tasks (see 4.7)	Coordination
2.2	2	Shifting investment and user requirements	3	2	The content analysis landscape is very dynamic, and an agile approach is therefore being adopted for its development	Low Demand
2.4	1	SOP from De Zeeuw et al. does not function on Snellius.	3	3	Consult with SURF partners	Technical
2.4	2	No other cohorts wanting to invest in linkage project	1	2	Through multiple consortia in NL we are well connected to approach PIs	Low Demand
2.4	3	Ethical barriers to linkage	1	3	SURF as TTP is accepted	Legal
2.4	4	Not possible to develop MZ-DZ algorithm	2	2	Develop analytical strategy (mixture models); explore linkage to databases of data on newborns	Technical
Laboratory						
3.1	1	The data required to undertake the study is not available or unsuitable for large scale analysis.	2	1	Manually curate the data for eventual large scale processing.	FAIR
3.1	2	Parental consent will be required to pursue the proposed research questions.	1	3	Pursue a synthetic data approach	Legal
3.1	3	Collaborating organisations are no longer able to participate	1	2	Pursue a synthetic data approach	Coordination
3.1	4	The technical expertise within the Maastricht team is no longer available.	2	1	Recruit a new researcher or involve one of the other 25 researchers at the Institute of Data Science.	Staffing

Task	num	Risk	Prob	Imp	Mitigating Action	Risk Area
3.3	1	Interest in ODISSEI LISS Calls is limited	1	3	Invest more efforts in advertising the Calls, and promotion of the possibilities the Calls offers	Low Demand
3.3	2	Interest in ODISSEI LISS Calls is overwhelming, leading to very low award rate	2	2	Make calls more thematically focused; merge funds for two calls; limit the target population to e.g. early career researchers only	High Demand
3.3	3	Attrition LISS panel is non-random making the panel less representative of the Dutch (speaking) population	2	3	Intensify panel care; correct for biases with stratified refreshment samples; increase efforts to minimize attrition; if needed reallocate budget to fund additional refreshment samples	Technical
3.3	4	Response rates decrease in monthly questionnaires and experiments fielded in the LISS panel	2	2	Motivate respondents to participate using response-enhancing measures, e.g. attractiveness of questionnaires and experiments, higher monetary incentives	Technical
3.3	5	Many panel members stop participating due to personal data breaches	1	3	Continuously monitor data security. Act proactively in case of a personal data breach or data leak	Legal
3.3	6	Increasing number of respondents opt-out when asked permission to link LISS data to register data, making linking less attractive for scientific research	2	2	Better explain what linking entails and that no identifying information will be made public	Technical
3.3	7	Delay in dissemination data via the LISS Data Archive due to restricted personnel capacity	1	2	Increase capacity; prioritize disseminations (first disseminate modules core study, then ODISSEI LISS Call projects, followed by other projects)	FAIR
3.3	8	Funding via the Domeinplan-SSH stops	1	3	Intensify efforts to acquire external funding	Sustainability
Hub						
4.1	1	Researchers are hard to reach and/or too busy	2	3	The team will keep events concise. The team will make information easily accessible online.	Coordination
4.1	2	Community Managers do not have enough scientific knowledge	2	2	The team will have regular meetings with the entire Coordination Team, to keep up to date.	Staffing
4.1	3	An overload of ODISSEI communication, which lessens the interest of potential users.	1	2	The team will keep track of communication output in a Content Calendar.	Low Demand
4.2	1	Researchers are hard to reach and/or too busy	2	3	The education team will keep ODISSEI events concise. It will strive to match what it offers to researchers' needs and concentrate efforts in an intensive summer school.	Low Demand
4.2	2	Task team members do not have enough scientific knowledge	2	2	The task team will have regular meetings with the rest of the Coordination Team, to keep up to date. It will work closely with partners who do have specific knowledge on specific topics.	Staffing
4.2	3	Demand for courses is too high	2	2	The task team will scale up events, and when needed it will assist in	High Demand

Task	num	Risk	Prob	Imp	Mitigating Action	Risk Area
					coordinating 'train the trainer' events in cooperation with ODISSEI partners.	
4.2	4	Demand for training is too low	2	3	The task team will work with the Community Management task (4.1) to increase ODISSEI's visibility, so information about the events can be spread as wide as possible.	Low Demand
4.3	1	Not obtaining appropriate time investments from researchers	1	3	Selection of researchers based on time commitment (in addition to project criteria), e.g., the researchers (not SoDa) carry main responsibility for substantive papers with SoDa collaboration	Coordination
4.3	2	Not reaching the non-academic researchers (e.g. planbureaus)	3	1	None (not actively seeking out collabs, but open to them); reusability of software products -> possibility of usage outside academia (see ASReview)	Coordination
4.3	3	Not being able to keep the team's knowledge state of the art	3	2	No person on earth has state-of-the-art knowledge. Mitigation is continuing training & education in collaboration with UU Information & Technology Services (ITS) and NLeScC; collaboration with experts in our network (e.g. UU focus area ADS)	Staffing
4.3	4	In the team, not being able to cover the wide range of required skills	1	3	(1) By spending 1 fte on wide expertise of UU ITS team, wide range of skills available; (2) network of experts in UU focus area ADS (3) participating in SIGs of NLeScC.	Staffing
4.3	5	Not finding sufficient projects	2	3	Active acquisition, close collaboration with community management, close collaboration with operational management	Low Demand
4.4	1	Fewer applications than expected	2	2	Allocate the remaining available money to the next call round to award more grants than initially planned.	Low Demand
4.4	2	Not reaching sufficient social scientists	2	3	Collaborating with the ODISSEI community managers to plan and organize an information day regarding the call for social science researchers. Enhance visibility through newsletters and social media.	Coordination
4.4	3	More applications than expected	2	2	Move funding forward to grant more projects, and acquire more funding for periods 2 & 3. Limit the scope of the calls, for example by using a thematic call, focussing on specific technologies (e.g., geospatial, visual analytics, etc.)	High Demand
4.4	4	Projects that are too complex to fit within the available hours	2	2	Organize information day and consultations hours with NLeScC and SoDa teams to advise on a fitting project plan.	Sustainability
4.4	5	No funding available for calls in 2024 and beyond (needs additional funding)	2	3	Explore options for a joint eScience - ODISSEI call early in the process, after the first call round (i.e., early 2022).	Sustainability

<i>Task</i>	<i>num</i>	<i>Risk</i>	<i>Prob</i>	<i>Imp</i>	<i>Mitigating Action</i>	<i>Risk Area</i>
4.5	1	Difficulties in recruitment of challenge participants	2	3	Embedded within the ODISSEI-SICSS Summer School and collaboration with the Fragile Families Project	Low Demand
4.5	2	No interest from social scientists	1	3	Embedded within the ODISSEI-SICSS Summer School and collaboration with the Fragile Families Project	Low Demand

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